

Sustainability of Debt Relief on Poverty Alleviation in Nigeria

Oluwatosin R. Ifaloye

Department of political science and international relations
Covenant University

Email: oluwatosin.ifaloye@covenantuniversity.edu.ng

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0003-6706-4121>

Adenike E. Onabote

Department of political science and international relations
Covenant University

Email: adenike.onabotepgs@stu.cu.edu.ng (Corresponding author)

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0002-3937-4627>

Felix C. Chidozie

Department of political science and international relations
Covenant University

Email: felix.chidozie@covenantuniversity.edu.ng

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2187-9187>

Abstract

Background: Nigeria is rich in natural resources and has the largest population in Africa, yet it remains entrenched in poverty. Many attempts have been made to improve the lives of the people, yet the majority still live below the poverty line. Debt relief is one such attempt at reducing poverty; however, the sustainability of debt relief is highly debatable.

Objective: This study explores the sustainability of debt relief as a strategy for alleviating poverty in Nigeria.

Methodology: The study employs an exploratory design that involves qualitative data collection through in-depth interviews of international relations specialists. Secondary data from published research is employed to support the analysis to obtain a complete picture of debt relief and its impact.

Result: The findings indicate that while debt relief provided temporary economic relief and allowed for the short-term stabilisation of Nigeria's economy, its long-term poverty reduction impacts are constrained. Corruption, inappropriate fiscal management, and stringent debt relief terms often counterbalance its benefits. The study also highlights that long-term poverty reduction relies on good governance, policy implementation, and institutional reform.

Conclusion: The study concludes that there is no meaningful long-term nexus between debt relief and poverty alleviation in Nigeria. Debt relief cannot be a sustainable solution for poverty without improvements in governance and structural reforms.

Unique Contribution: This study provides empirical evidence of Nigeria's debt relief-poverty reduction nexus, emphasising the need for sustainable economic policy independent of external debt relief.

Key Recommendation: The government of Nigeria must accord the utmost priority to institutional reforms to enhance transparency, accountability, and effective resource utilization so that economic relief can lead to effective poverty alleviation.

Keywords: Debt relief, Governance, International relations, Nigeria, Poverty alleviation, sustainability.

Introduction

Poverty remains one of Nigeria's most pressing challenges despite the nation's vast natural resources and status as Africa's most populous country (Aderounmu et al., 2021). Persistent efforts to eradicate poverty, including various economic programs and international interventions, have yielded limited success, with a significant portion of the population still living below the poverty line (Elomien et al., 2024). One such strategy is external debt relief, which allows states to free up resources for key public investments in health, education, and infrastructure, which are drivers of economic growth and poverty reduction.

External debt has become a double-edged sword for many developing countries, including Nigeria. Borrowing from international creditors gives room for financing vital development projects. However, the inability to service these debts usually leads to severe economic crises, as a huge percentage of yearly national budgets is used to service debts (Ekperiware & Oladeji, 2012). Debt relief is recognised as a solution to this crisis and has been implemented in various forms to stimulate economic growth. However, the sustainability of debt relief as a poverty alleviation strategy remains contentious, especially in Nigeria, where governance challenges, corruption, and unfavourable conditions are often attached to debt relief. The relationship between debt relief and the poverty reduction nexus is examined in the Nigerian context. The paper draws on expert qualitative interviews and a desk review of the extant literature to discuss how immediate and structural factors impede Nigeria's long-term benefits of debt relief. The application was found for the dependency theory; it was used to analyse how debt relief can perpetuate cycles of dependency and underdevelopment.

Literature review

External Debt

External debt refers to a country's total debt to foreign creditors such as other governments, international financial institutions, or private lenders outside the country's borders (Ogbonna et al., 2021). External debt is also known as any form of money lent to a country that has been utilised in the receiving country and has not been repaid to the lending country (Ogbonna & Appah, 2016).

External Debt can be used to fund developmental investments or to fund the budget deficit. However, external debt must be managed because a large amount can lead to economic challenges, including debt overhang, high debt service payments, and a potential risk to the country's financial stability and economic growth. Since there are insufficient financial resources at home, borrowing is done through international sources. Third-world nations obtain their external debt from multilateral organisations such as the London Club and Paris Club creditors, promissory note holders, and other creditors. External debt can add meaningful gains to the economy of the receiving state. However, servicing of debt payments usually hinders economic growth in the future.

External debt relief

Debt relief is often seen as a solution for reducing the burden of external debt, particularly in heavily indebted developing countries (Sulaiman & Azeez, 2012). These would then take the forms of debt forgiveness, debt restructuring, or concessional lending terms. External debt relief is perceived as a critical initiative to promote economic stability and development for heavily indebted countries. High levels of debt stock burden hinder economic growth, reduce fiscal freedom for important public services, and increase vulnerability to financial crises.

Programmes and initiatives launched over the years to provide external debt relief to heavily indebted countries take on unilaterally executed action by creditor nations, and those as part of a multilateral effort with international agencies like the IMF and the World Bank. Notable among them is the Heavily Indebted Poor Countries debt relief programme initiated by the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund in 1996. According to Essers & Cassimon (2023), the HIPC Initiative aims to reduce the external debt burden of poor countries that were heavily indebted to reasonable levels. It is usually a mix of debt forgiveness, rescheduling, and concessional financing. Other notable projects include the Multilateral Debt Relief Initiative proposed by the IMF and the World Bank in 2005. The MDRI enables the cancellation of the remaining debt obligations of those low-income countries eligible for the IMF, the World Bank, and the African Development Fund.

Debt relief in Nigeria

The debt relief initiative in Nigeria in 2005 is often cited as a success story in reducing the country's external debt burden, with scholars such as Adepoju, Salau, and Obayelu (2007) praising the agreement for providing substantial economic respite. Nigeria's agreement under the Policy Support Instrument (PSI) granted 60% debt forgiveness, expected to catalyse the nation's economic recovery and provide resources for development projects aimed at poverty alleviation (Aluko & Arowolo, 2010). With Nigeria being granted debt relief of 18 billion USD, the funds freed up from debt relief were expected to be used to boost the economy by creating jobs, stimulating economic activities and investing in various developmental projects in different sectors like power, infrastructure, education, health, agriculture, security amongst others to spur economic growth. The funds saved due to debt relief were also recognised as instrumental in achieving the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs).

Implementing the debt relief initiative was expected to help Nigeria maintain a manageable level of external debt without adversely affecting Nigeria's growth and development. Since Nigeria was

expected to lose the title of being a heavily indebted country, it was expected that the socio-political and investment environment would become more favourable to stimulate economic activities and create wealth. Despite debt relief received under Olusegun Obasanjo's administration, succeeding administrations have been on a borrowing spree, which has resulted in an increase in public debt in recent years (Okodua, Akpesiri, & Ewetan, 2022).

Theoretical framework

This research adopted the Dependency Theory to assess the sustainability of debt relief as a poverty-alleviation tool in Nigeria. The dependency theory, developed in the mid-20th century by scholars such as Andre Gunder Frank, challenges the neoclassical economic perspective on how developing nations can progress through incorporation into the global economy. Instead, the dependency theorist believes that the global economic system is built so that the wealthy nations, often referred to as 'the centre', exploit the poorer states, "the periphery".

Concerning external debt relief, dependency theory places meaning on the reality that the financial relationships between creditor countries and debtor nations, such as Nigeria, have been structured to perpetuate economic dependency, underdevelopment, and poverty. What is a benevolent act for reducing the economic burden of developing nations in debt relief can reinforce a cycle of dependency, defining the periphery-centre relationship. In this regard, Nigeria, a developing nation, presently relies on loans from international financial institutions and creditor nations to finance key development projects. But with the inability of these nations to repay their loans, what was a noble gesture has grown into a heavy debt burden, with a large chunk of Nigeria's annual budget being utilised in servicing the debt rather than its development.

Dependency theory thus best explains Nigeria's debt situation as it puts into perspective the structure of the forces in action within the global financial system. Programs for debt relief, such as under the HIPC Initiative, may afford temporary financial respite but are usually accompanied by very stringent conditions that worsen the economic subordination of peripheral nations, one of which is the devaluation of the currency.

Other theories, such as the Modernisation and Neoliberalism theories, can be used to analyse Nigeria's debt relief and poverty alleviation. Modernisation theory holds that the developing world must pass through a series of developments and progress previously passed by those countries that have already industrialised. In this perspective, one only notices unequal power relations that create global financial relationships. Neoliberalism, as a doctrine of free markets and limited government interference, remains blind to the exploitative character of international debt relations. In contrast, dependency theory recognises that the structural inequalities embedded in the global economic system disproportionately benefit developed nations at the expense of developing ones. Nigeria's external debt situation, where significant resources are directed toward servicing loans rather than development, exemplifies this. Thus, dependency theory offers a more nuanced understanding of how debt relief initiatives may perpetuate underdevelopment despite their stated objectives by reinforcing Nigeria's financial dependency on creditor nations and institutions.

While dependency theory provides valuable insights into the structural inequalities that shape Nigeria's debt relations, it is not without limitations. Critics argue that the theory may oversimplify the dynamics of global finance, especially in the context of emerging economies like China playing a more prominent role in African development. Moreover, dependency theory tends to focus on external factors while sometimes underestimating the role of internal governance failures, such as corruption and mismanagement, which also play a significant role in Nigeria's debt challenges. To address these limitations, this study critically reflects on how dependency theory can be updated to reflect modern realities.

Methodology

This study adopts an exploratory research design to investigate the sustainability of debt relief as a poverty alleviation strategy in Nigeria. According to Pantano and Vannucci (2019), an exploratory design is used when one wants to get familiar with present realities, and that will be particularly useful for this research because only a few in-depth qualitative analyses have been done on the long-term impact of debt relief in the Nigerian context. This study explores the opinions of experts and secondary data in understanding how debt reduction impacts poverty alleviation, both in terms of immediate effects and structural challenges. The primary data was sourced through six semi-structured, in-depth interviews with international relations and economic diplomacy experts. The respondents included four researchers from NIIA, one professor, and one doctor. The data was sourced from persons with first-hand information on the debt relief efforts by Nigeria and how they relate to poverty alleviation, on which the research is based. The study used a purposive sampling method to get data from individuals with direct knowledge of Nigeria's debt relief efforts and its relationship with poverty alleviation. Other secondary data were derived from journals, books, government reports, and verified Internet sources.

Thematic analysis was used to analyse the data from the in-depth interviews, where key themes were identified in the data related to the research questions. This involves a reading of the interview transcripts and then a coding process where responses are categorised into themes such as "governance challenges," "corruption and mismanagement," "economic restructuring conditions," and "temporary financial relief."

Manual coding was done; however, it was systematic. The codes were refined, and the data were continuously reviewed. For the secondary data analysis, content analysis was used to identify information supporting and rejecting the findings from the primary data. This entailed critically reviewing key reports and academic literature on Nigeria's national debt relief initiatives and their long-term impact on poverty alleviation.

Data presentation and analysis

Debt relief has been identified as a policy Nigeria seeks to pursue internationally through diplomacy. To understand the research objective and receive suitable answers, the respondents were asked about the relationship between debt relief and poverty alleviation in Nigeria.

Respondent 5 mentioned that,

Diplomacy attracted some level of success in helping to reduce the nation's external debt, and having a lot of it cancelled gave the country's finances a big respite. So, that was seen as a significant economic success. At the time, the Nigerian economy was rebalanced as it became the largest economy in Africa. It used to be seen as the 2nd largest behind South Africa, but during the first two terms of the Obasanjo administration, it was revised and is now the largest economy.

Respondent 6 further stated,

On debt relief, Obasanjo popularised this; he secured debt forgiveness. And when a country is free of debt, then that means it will strengthen the naira. Because Nigeria is heavily indebted today, you can do little or nothing once you are in debt. Debt service alone is taking too much of our resources. And that is why people are in poverty. I can tell you that under Obasanjo, there was a commitment on his part to make Nigeria great. And the foreign powers saw that commitment, that desire, that dedication, that trust, and granted debt forgiveness.

When exploring the relationship between debt relief and poverty alleviation, Respondent 5 stated that.

Well, it has freed up the government, a burden. It allowed the government to have a more extensive foreign reserve, and it allowed the government to invest in what was called, at the time, an inclusive economic package. There was a series of poverty reduction initiatives. Some of them are called short starts. Some of them are in the education sector, in youth empowerment. You have all of that happen. But part of the problem is that we have yet to see much impact because we have too many mouths to feed. Yes. And very few resources to look after them. So, it is as if what has been done has simply been a drop in the ocean.

Respondent 2, meanwhile, referred to the Obasanjo administration and stated, "Now that the government was expected to use the money to pursue the Sustainable Development Goals. But you and I know that not much has been achieved. Some of this money has ended up in the private pocket, not development projects that would give a better life to Nigerians."

Respondent 1 similarly mentioned that "It is not just about campaigning. It is about making judicious use of our resources. I do not think Nigeria lacks money, and I do not think Nigeria lacks resources. I think we lack meaningful leaders who would have administered even these resources to benefit the people." Respondent 1 further stated that

We have yet to show enough, at least, or prove beyond a reasonable doubt that we want our debt to be relieved, considering the level of wastage and monumental corruption from government officials and those in positions of authority. We have not proven beyond a reasonable doubt to the world that we are asking for debt relief. And we've even been going on a borrowing spree.

Respondent 4, on the other hand, recognised how debt relief allowed the government to focus on different developmental projects, stating that

Once that humongous amount was written off, Nigeria had enough funds and resources to embark on other projects, develop our economy, pay our staff, and look at all those areas. The debt relief helped the Nigerian government embark on major projects and meet her domestic needs. After our administration, I need to find out if any other governments have even asked for debt relief or if they have been able to gain one.

Respondent 3 believed that debt relief always has strings to debt relief, which makes it incapable of alleviating poverty.

There are no free lunches. The country that is giving you debt relief, what are they asking for in return? So, they'll ask you to, as we saw on that structural adjustment programme, they will ask you to go and restructure your economy. Restructuring means positioning yourself well for maximum exploitation and, for example, devaluing your currency. Once you devalue your currency, you are buying from them at a cheaper rate. Open and liberalise the economy, open up your market, etc. These are terms and conditions that have yet to do much for Africa. All in the name that you are getting debt relief. Debt that was incurred and wastefully or corruptly spent.

While speaking on the sustainability that debt relief may have on poverty alleviation, Respondent 3 stated,

We've gotten debt relief and forgiveness, but here we are again. Some scholars say this debt relief, just like aid, is a problem. Once you forgive people, they never learn their lessons. So let them pay through their noses, so people who are wasteful, corrupt, ineffective, and inefficient in the management of their resources, there's no amount of debt you can forgive them, and they will learn their lessons. In fact, in the first place, we even question why we are in this debt.

Discussion of findings

The study found that from the interviews, debt relief has had mixed effects on alleviating poverty in Nigeria. Debt relief was recognised to have led to significant debt cancellation that brought financial relief and economic rebalancing into perspective, making Nigeria the largest African economy. It was also noted that the naira was strengthened through debt forgiveness under Obasanjo, and the financial burden was reduced to allow resources to be freed for development. However, this had little impact since the population living in poverty was more than the available resources, thus making the efforts seem like a drop in the ocean. Much of the funds released to pursue the Millennium Development Goals went into private pockets, not into development projects. This is similar to the argument by Folorunso, Duruji, & Chidozie (2024), who, upon observing a high incidence of corruption in Nigeria, said the country needed an internal purge.

The Respondents also criticised the misuse of resources, having noted that Nigeria's problems result from a lack of good leadership rather than a lack of money. They also highlighted the problematic conditions usually attached to debt relief, such as economic restructuring and devaluation, which can undermine long-term benefits and sustainability. While the study realised that debt relief provided temporary financial relief, long-term effectiveness in the poverty alleviation objective was limited by corruption, mismanagement, and unfavourable conditions coming with the relief. It took more than that, good governance and judicious use of finances to alleviate poverty in Nigeria sustainably.

This finding was supported by Ahiadorme (2023), who focused on establishing the impacts of debt relief in emerging and developing economies. The result showed that the given debt relief could not change or correct the statuses of these countries concerning their debts. Similarly, Ayoola & Segun-Olufemi (2022) critically analysed the processes that led to debt relief in 2005 and its effect on the socio-economic well-being of the people from 2006 to 2019. Their findings showed that creditors granted relief to debtors, but it wasn't entirely an altruistic act. The debtors, on the other hand, failed to maximise gains, which worsened the financial mismanagement of politicians, leading to more accrued debt not too long after being granted relief at the detriment of the population with a high rate of unemployment, infrastructural deficit, high poverty rate, amongst others. They then said that the requirements to be granted debt relief would need to be evaluated with more stringent measures, ensuring a beneficial effect on the receiving state and its people while managing the total debt stock to avoid a debt circle.

This corroborates the study of Olalere & Olatunji (2023), who pointed out how it is interesting that debt has a unique way of robbing a debtor nation of its sovereignty and independence. This is because a country would be at the mercy of its creditors if it cannot service its debt. An excellent example is what was widely reported: the Chinese took control of Zambia's airport since Zambia could not pay back the debts it had received from China. As a result, its independence and sovereignty were compromised. Chidozie, et al. (2020) also found that the globalised capitalist system, as propagated by Western states, still needs to improve the living conditions of people living in developing nations.

It was also found that a false narrative about debt relief is being created. In the figure shown below, we find that Nigeria recorded the highest ODA between 2005 and 2006. This was because the debt relief granted to Nigeria was counted as ODA. This gives an impression of increased aid when, in reality, the funds are not new or additional but rather a restructuring of existing debts. While debt relief might contribute to a country's fiscal health, counting it as ODA is fiction because it inflates aid figures without immediate and direct resources for poverty alleviation.

When Nigeria returned to democracy in 1999, despite paying about USD 48.43 billion to creditors from 1980 to 2004, Nigeria's external debt increased to USD 35.94 billion in 2004 (Ugwuja et al., 2019). However, with a renewed focus on economic diplomacy, the external debt decreased from 36% of GDP in 2004 to less than 4% in 2007. However, Nigeria's debt situation is paradoxical, as shown in Figure 2; despite effective management under Obasanjo, it has increased significantly due to poor management and excessive borrowing by successive governments, and this questions

the effectiveness and sustainability of debt relief on poverty alleviation in Nigeria. Since then, they have been no significant campaign for debt relief except till the Buhari administration, when various countries, particularly developing states, as agreed in the 2015 Paris Agreement on Debt for Climate (DFC) deal, began to clamour for debt forgiveness of developing states, whose debts would be channelled towards climate issues.

Thus, this study concludes that debt relief is not a sustainable strategy for poverty alleviation in Nigeria based on the following findings:

1. Corruption and mismanagement hinder the proper utilisation of resources freed by debt relief.
2. Debt relief often comes with terms like economic restructuring and devaluation that undermine benefits in the long run.
3. Despite previous success, successive governments' poor management and excessive borrowing have led to a debt cycle.

Table 1. Chart showing Net Official Development Assistance Received in Nigeria Between 1999 to 2022

Source: World Bank (2023)

Table 2: Chart showing External Debt Stocks of Nigeria Between 1999 to 2022

Source: World Bank (2023)

Recommendations and Conclusion

This study examined the sustainability of debt relief on poverty alleviation in Nigeria, focusing on its long-term impact. The study reviewed the literature on key concepts of external debt, debt relief,

and recent studies on debt relief in Nigeria. Through the lens of dependency theory, the study illustrates how debt relief, as currently structured, reinforces Nigeria's dependency on external financial institutions. Structural conditions imposed by international financial institutions, such as economic restructuring, further entrench this dependency.

The findings reveal that while debt relief initiatives, such as the 2005 debt relief program, provided significant short-term financial relief and allowed Nigeria to rebalance its economy, their long-term impact on poverty alleviation has been hindered by systemic governance failures, corruption, and unfavourable conditions attached to the relief. These internal governance challenges have limited Nigeria's ability to fully harness the benefits of debt relief, resulting in a cycle of dependency and re-indebtedness.

Based on these findings, this study recommends governance reforms to ensure transparency, accountability, and resource management in Nigeria. Independent oversight bodies should be instituted to monitor where and how freed resources are utilised in poverty alleviation projects. The study also recommends that international financial institutions, such as the IMF and World Bank, revise the conditions for debt relief by shifting from purely economic restructuring to governance reforms that will offer better resource management. It is also suggested that Nigerian policymakers must ensure that resources released by debt relief are used in support of long-term poverty-reduction programs. This implies investment in developing all-inclusive economic growth, job creation, and extending health, education, and social protection programs. It is also essential that Nigeria engage in regional collaborations with other neighbouring countries facing similar debt challenges. This also calls for advocacy for more favourable debt relief terms and accountability in using freed resources at various platforms, such as the African Union and ECOWAS.

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